

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Development of Varicose Vein: Today & Tomorrow

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 01 April. 2025

Keywords:

Varicose Vein, Chronic Venous Insufficiency, Superficial venous thrombosis, Deep Vein Thrombosis, Sclerotherapy.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15117741

ABSTRACT

Chronic venous insufficiency or CVI, is a condition in which veins have problems moving blood back to the heart. With long-term (chronic) venous insufficiency, vein walls are weakened and valves are damaged. Chronic venous insufficiency can develop from common conditions such as Varicose Veins. It is a common condition characterized by enlarged, twisted, blue or purple bulging and painful veins, typically affecting the lower extremities of the body. It's noteworthy that even in the absence of obvious bulging veins, the term "varicose veins" is frequently used to describe superficial venous reflux. Simply put, these are known as "hidden varicose veins." A weakening of the venous valves and walls is a common cause of varicose veins. Blood might flow back and pool in veins due to damaged valves, causing them to enlarge. Weakened vein walls are longer, broader, and less elastic than normal, causing valve flaps to split, resulting in increased blood pooling and twisted veins. Usually, varicose veins worsen, causing pain, enlarged ankles, skin damage, leg ulcers, venous bleeding, and superficial venous thrombosis. A weakening of the venous valves and walls is a common cause of varicose veins. Blood might flow back and pool in veins due to damaged valves, causing them to enlarge. Weakened vein walls are longer, broader, and less elastic than normal, causing valve flaps to split, resulting in increased blood pooling and twisted veins.

INTRODUCTION

The Latin term "Varix," which meaning "twisted," is where the word "varicose" originates. A "vein with a saccular development tortuous," as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), is a varicose vein. The word "varicosity" refers

generically to lengthy, twisted, pouched, thickened, friable, inelastic vessels that have similarly changed over time and are continuously losing their valvular efficiency. [7]. Varicose veins are defined as dilated, tortuous, subcutaneous

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

veins ≥ 3 mm in diameter measured in the upright position with demonstrable reflux. [1-3]

Fig 1.1 Varicose Veins forms in a lower extremity.

Anatomy

The superficial and deep venous systems carry venous blood from the lower limbs back to the right heart against gravity. Great saphenous veins (GSV), small saphenous veins (SSV), and their

tributaries make up the superficial venous system. [1, 3]. The medial end of the dorsal venous arch is where the GSV begins. Veins are blood vessels located throughout the body that collect oxygen-poor blood and return it to the heart. Veins are part of the circulatory system.

Fig: 1.2 Anatomical view of Varicose Vein

Pathogenesis

Varicose veins develop when the valves in the veins fail to function properly, leading to a

backward flow of blood. These valves normally act like one-way doors, allowing blood to flow towards the heart and preventing it from flowing backward. [4, 5]. When these valves become weak

or damaged, blood pools in the veins, causing them to swell and become visible. This pooling of blood can also put pressure on the surrounding tissues, leading to symptoms such as pain, fatigue, and swelling. [6]. The mechanism of valve failure is complex and can be influenced by factors such as age, genetics, and lifestyle. Factors like prolonged standing or sitting, pregnancy, and obesity can further increase pressure in the veins, contributing to valve dysfunction. The weakened valve system ultimately leads to the characteristic appearance of varicose veins. [4]. It is due to the various factors such as, Environmental and Patient factors, Genetic Predisposition, Local Hypoxia, Hemodynamic factors, Alteration in the extracellular matrix

- 1) Changes in the vein wall & over stretching of veins
- 2) Increases in size of veins but valve leaflets do not expand
- 3) Secondary valvular Incompetence & Backflow (Reflux)
- 4) Pooling and further dilation of veins
- 5) Varicosity – Dilated Tortuous Veins

Diagnosis and Evaluation

1. Doppler Ultrasound:

Doppler ultrasound helps with varicose veins detection and identifying severity. It is a special procedure to examine blood circulation.

Uses:

- ✓ A Doppler ultrasound uses sound waves to produce images of blood moving through circulatory system.
- ✓ Peripheral arterial diseases (PAD), narrow or blocked arteries in our legs or arms.
- ✓ Blood clots, including deep vein thrombosis (DVT), Blood clots usually in the legs.
- ✓ Chronic venous insufficiency (CVI).
- ✓ Tumors in blood vessels.

2. Venography:

- ✓ A venogram (venography) is an X-ray procedure that shows blood flow in the veins.
- ✓ Providers typically use this test to look at veins in the: Legs, Pelvis, Upper arms.

Uses:

- ✓ Diagnose deep vein thrombosis (DVT) when ultrasound is inconclusive or can't provide a good enough view (for example, when there's swelling around an arm or leg).
- ✓ Diagnose blood flow problems in the pelvic area, including pelvic congestion syndrome, nutcracker syndrome and varicoceles. [22].
- ✓ Check blood flow in the leg veins before certain surgeries, like varicose vein stripping and ligation.
- ✓ Provide real-time imaging during treatments, like thrombolytic therapy and thrombectomy.

Fig. 2.1 Venogram

3. Ankle-brachial index (ABI):

This test measures blood pressure in the ankles and arms to determine the severity of arterial blockage and rule out other vascular conditions. [2, 3].

Uses:

- ✓ The ankle-brachial index test is done to check for PAD [Peripheral Arterial Diseases] — narrowed arteries that reduce blood flow, usually in the legs.
- ✓ Risk factors for PAD include: History of tobacco use, Diabetes, High blood pressure & Cholesterol.

Treatment of Varicose Vein

The conventional treatments for varicose veins involve compression therapies- employment of particular type of surgeries like cryosurgery, vein stripping, ambulatory phlebectomy. [4] The Non-surgical treatments mainly involve sclerotherapy and endothermal ablation. [5, 6].

1. Physical Therapy [6]
2. Compression Therapy [6]

Types of compression therapy device includes:

- ✓ Compression stockings [2,7]
- ✓ Bandages and wraps
- ✓ Inflatable devices

1. Surgical Therapy:

A. Vein Stripping: Vein stripping is a surgical procedure that removes or ties off a large vein in the leg to treat varicose veins and other chronic venous diseases [2, 3]. The side effects are produced by this therapy that are bleeding, infections, bruising [5, 6]. Stripping of varicose veins out surgically does not permanently remove veins, as most grow back but without valves, during the healing process, causing the same problem to reoccur. [3, 4].

B. Ambulatory Phlebectomy: In this technique by achieving laceration in the skin the superficial veins are removed. After this treatment the temporary inflammation and swelling may be observed [5].

2. Non-Surgical Treatments: The Non-surgical treatments mainly include Sclerotherapy, Ultrasound guided foam sclerotherapy and Endothermal Ablation. [3,7].

A. Sclerotherapy: By using this therapy, the spider veins or angioectasis are treated. For this treatment some sclerosing agents are used like as sodium salicylate, chromated glycerine they are administered by using small needles:

Fig.2.3 Sclerotherapy- Injecting a solution directly into varicose vein

Prevention of Varicose Vein

In most of the cases, varicose veins can be cured by early preventive measures such as,

- ✓ Maintaining a Healthy Weight
- ✓ Regular Exercise
- ✓ Avoid Prolonged Standing or Sitting

Novel Approach of Varicose Vein

<p>1. Name of Drug: Varithena 1% Approved by FDA: Originally in 2014 Active Ingredient: Polidocanol Drug Product: Polidocanol injectable (1.0%) Brand name: Asclera Class of Drug: Sclerosing agent, Vasosclerator</p>	
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[Table 1: Polidocanol]

1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical Description • Color • Odour • Taste 	White Pungent Bitter & Unpleasant
2.	BCS Class	Class III
3.	Solubility	Hygroscopic, Limited solubility in water & alcohol
4.	p ^H (solution at 3% w/v)	4.0 - 7.5

5.	Melting Point Range	21 - 27°C
6.	Density at 45°C	0.987 g/cm ³
7.	Molecular formula	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ (OCH ₂ -CH ₂ -), OH
8.	Route of Administration	Intravenous Route
9.	Mean Molecular	Approximately 600.

Mechanism of Action

Step 1: Direct Injection into varicose veins
 Step 2: Damage to the endothelial cells, leading to disruption of cell membrane integrity
 Step 3: Triggers an inflammatory response → WBCs and platelets aggregation

Step 4: Fibrinogen is converted to fibrin, forming a blood clot.

Step 5: Due to replacement of fibrotic tissue → Vein wall thickening and contraction

Step 6: Fibrotic tissue contracts, causing the vein to narrow and close → Blood flow is redirected to adjacent veins.

2. Name Of Drug: Rivaroxaban

Approved by FDA: Originally in 2011, in October 2019 it was Approved to prevent blood clots.

Brand name: Xarelto

Generic name: Rivaroxaban

Dosage form: Tablets and Oral Suspension (10mg, 15mg)

Class of Drug: Anti - Coagulate

[Table 2: Rivaroxaban]

1.	Physical Description <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Color • Odor • Taste 	White to Off white Odorless Bitter
2.	Molecular weight	435.89 g/mol
3.	Solubility	Water: Practically insoluble, Ethanol: Soluble
4.	pH	6.8-7.2
5.	Melting Point Range	220-225°C
6.	Density	1.43 g/cm ³
7.	Molecular formula	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S
8.	Route of Administration	Oral Route

Mechanism of Action

Step 1: Inhibition of Factor Xa
 Step 2: Prevention of Prothrombinase Complex Formation

Step 3: Reduction of Thrombin Generation

Step 4: Inhibition of Fibrin Clot Formation

Step 5: Prevention of Blood Coagulation

3. Name Of Drug: Apixaban Approved by: Initial U.S approval 2012 Brand name: ELIQUIS Generic name: Apixaban Dosage form: Tablets and Oral Use (2.5mg and 5 mg) Class of Drug: Anti - Coagulate	
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[Table 3: Apixaban]

1.	Physical Description <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Color • Odor • Taste 	Pale Yellow Film- coated Odorless Tasteless
2.	Molecular weight	419.45 g/mol
3.	Solubility	Slightly Soluble in water & freely soluble in methanol
4.	pH	4.5-6.5(Slightly acidic to neutral)
5.	Melting Point Range	165-170°C
6.	Density	1.43 g/cm ³
7.	Molecular formula	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₄
8.	Route of Administration	Oral Route

Mechanism of Action

Step: 1 Inhibition of Factor Xa

Step: 2 Blockage of Prothrombinase Complex

Step: 3 Decreased Thrombin Formation

Step: 4 Prevention of Platelet Activation

Step: 5 Inhibition of Coagulation Cascade

4. Name Of Drug: Ticagrelor Approved by FDA: Initial U.S approval 201 Brand name: Brilinta Generic name: Ticagrelor Dosage form: Tablets and Oral Suspension (90mg) Class of Drug: Anti - Platelet	
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[Table: 4 Ticagrelor]

1.	Physical Description <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Color • Odor • Taste 	Yellow- Pale Yellow Round & Film Coated Odorless Mild, slightly sweet or neutral taste
2.	Molecular weight	522.65 g/mol
3.	Solubility	Water: Practically insoluble, Ethanol: Soluble
4.	pH	5.5- 6.5
5.	Melting Point Range	184-188°C
6.	Density	1.43 g/cm ³
7.	Molecular formula	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ F ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S
8.	Route of Administration	Oral Route

Mechanism of Action

- Step 1: Inhibition of P2Y₁₂ Receptor
 Step 2: Increased cAMP Levels
 Step 3: Reduced Platelet Activation

- Step 4: Endothelial Function Enhancement
 Step 5: Prostacyclin (PGI₂) Increase
 Step 6: Reduced Inflammation and Oxidative Stress

<p>5. Name Of Drug: Dabigatran Etexilate Approved by: Initial U.S approval 2010 Brand name: PRADAXA Generic name: Dabigatran Etexilate Dosage form: Capsule (75mg and 150mg) Class of Drug: Anti – Coagulate & Direct Thrombin Inhibitor</p>	
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1.	Physical Description	Yellow
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Color • Odor • Taste 	Odorless Tasteless
2.	Molecular weight	407.47 g/mol
3.	Solubility	Soluble in water, methanol & ethanol
4.	p ^H	4.6-5.6 (Slightly acidic to neutral)
5.	Melting Point Range	180-185°C
6.	Density	1.45 g/cm ³
7.	Molecular formula	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₃

Mechanism of Action

- Step 1: Oral administration results into absorption from stomach & small intestine
 Step 2 Dabigatran Etexilate is hydrolyzed to Dabigatran by esterases
 Step 3: Dabigatran distributes to tissues, including the liver, kidneys, and vascular wall
 Step 4: Dabigatran binds reversibly to thrombin (Factor IIa)
 Step 5: Thrombin's activity is inhibited, preventing: Conversion of fibrinogen to fibrin → Activation of Factor XIII → Platelet aggregation
 Step 6: Reduced thrombin activity decreases blood clot formation

CONCLUSION

Varicose veins are a prevalent and complex condition affecting millions of people worldwide. The understanding of varicose vein development and emergence of Novel approaches for varicose veins marks a significant shift in the treatment & offering improved patient outcomes. Anticoagulants and Anti-inflammatory drugs for Varicose Veins are characterized by inflammation and blood clotting. Anticoagulants and anti-inflammatory drugs target these pathways, alleviating symptoms and slowing disease progression. All drugs which we have discussed in this review have a significant in their mode of action and therapy of varicose veins. Further

research is necessary to elucidate the mechanism & optimize the therapeutic action.

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HOW TO CITE: Ishita Vekariya*, Morvi Raval, Arati Bhetariya, Dr. Chintankumar Tank, Vandana Ghul, Yash Mori, Drashti Bhalara, A Development of Varicose Vein: Today & Tomorrow, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 4, 26-34
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15117741>

